

DIVERSITY AND PROSPERITY OF MEDICINAL PLANTS FROM TELANGANA STATE, INDIA

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ABSTRACT

India is one of the mega biodiversity countries, having rich biodiversity, most of the plants using as medicines and others. Medicinal Plants utilization is known since times immemorial. These have been one of the important sources of medicines ever since the dawn of human civilization. The utility of medicinal plants played important role in Ayurveda, Unani, Siddha and also in modern medicine. 80% of world population utilizes drugs, derived from medicinal plants for their health security. The medicinal plants have various methods of preparation and application for different types of ailments and they have various preparation forms like crude, decoction, powder, and crushed and homogenized in water. Our Indian people have tremendous passion for medicinal plants and use of them for wide range of health related applications, especially our Telangana state have good topographic and geographical conditions to be a rich potential and diversity of Medicinal plants. In this study we encountered 240 medicinal Plants and their medicinal usages, therefore the documenting the medicinal plants and associated indigenous knowledge can be used as a basis for developing management plans for conservation and sustainable use of medicinal plants in the area.

KEYWORDS: Diversity, Documenting, Human, India, Medicinal Plants, Utilization.

INTRODUCTION

India is the mega biodiversity country, it has 15 agro climatic zones and 17000-18000 species of flowering plants of which 6000-7000 are estimated to have medicinal usage in folk and other documented systems of medicine, like Ayurveda, Siddha, Unani and Homoeopathy. About 960 species of medicinal plants are estimated to be in trade of which 178 species have annual consumption levels in excess of 100 metric tons. India is known for its rich vegetation and plant biodiversity, due to its geographical and climatic conditions. Medicinal plants are not only a major resource base for the traditional medicine and herbal industry but also provide livelihood and health security to a large segment of Indian population. The domestic trade of the AYUSH industry is of the order of Rs. 80 to 90 billion. There is global resurgence in traditional and alternative healthcare systems, resulting in world herbal trade which stands at US \$ 120 billion and is expected to reach US \$ 7 trillion by 2050. Indian share in the world trade, at present, however, is quite low (1-2%).

Medicinal Plants are one of the important sources of medicines ever since the dawn of human civilization. The utility of medicinal plants played important role in

Ayurveda, Unani, Siddha and also in modern medicine. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimated that 80% of the population of developing countries rely on traditional medicines, mostly plant based drugs, for their primary healthcare needs and security especially in Asia and African Countries (UNESCO 1996.) Even in modern pharmacopoeia still contains at least 25% drugs derived from plants and many others which are synthetic analogues built on prototype compounds isolated from plants. India and other countries have rich floristic yielding herbal drugs. The world market includes herbal drugs, pharmaceuticals, fragrances, flavors, dyes and other ingredients and their marketing exceeds several billion dollars per year (Biradar.2015).

Plants still remain as one of the major sources of drugs in modern as well as traditional system of medicine throughout the world. Medicinal plants chemically may have secondary metabolites like alkaloids, glycosides, steroids or other groups of compounds which have marked pharmaceutical action as anticancer, antimalarial, antidiabetic, antidiysenteric, *etc.* In spite of tremendous developments in the field of allopathy during the 20th century.

The world market for natural drugs, chemicals, pharmaceuticals, fragrances, flavors, and colour ingredients, exceeds several billion dollars per year. Examples include taxol, vincristine, vinblastine, colchicine, artemisinin, and the Indian ayurvedic drug-*forkolin*. Trade and market in medicinal plants is growing in volume and exports. It is estimated that the global trade in medicinal plants is US \$ 800 million per year. (Manoharachary and Nagaraju 2016 and Manoharachary *et al* 2017).

Topography, Climate of Telangana State

Telangana State is the youngest state in India; it was separated from the erstwhile Andhra Pradesh on 2nd June 2014, it has become 29th state of India on 2nd June 2014. Telangana State is situated on the Deccan Plateau, in the central stretch of the eastern seaboard of the Indian Peninsula Ranges between 15°50'-19°55' and 77°14'-78°50'E). The state has got 10 districts covering an area

of 133, 103 km. The most important rivers of the province are Musi, Krishna, Manjira and Godhavari. Dry deciduous, scrub Jungle forests and mixed forest types are distributed in Districts of Rangareddy, Khammam, Medak, Mahabubnagar, Warangal, Nizamabad and Adilabad. The annual rainfall is between 900 to 1500 mm in Northern Telangana and 700 to 900 mm in Southern Telangana, from the southwest monsoons. Various soil types include chalkas, red sandy soils, dubbas, deep red loamy soils, and very deep black cotton Soil. Telangana is a semi-arid area and has a predominantly hot and dry climate. Summers start in March, and reach peak in May with an average high temperatures to the 42°C (108°F) range. The monsoon arrives in June and lasts until September with about 755 mm (29.7 inches) of precipitation. A dry, mild winter starts in late November and lasts until early February with little humidity and an average temperature of 22.23 °C (72.73 °F) range.(Fig.1).

Figure-1: Study Area Map (Telangana State).

MEDICINAL PLANTS USAGE IN STUDY AREA

Human interest in medicinal plants is the re-emerging health aid has been fuelled by the rising costs of drugs used in the maintenance of personal health and well-being. Based on current research, medicinal plants will continue to play an important role as a health aid (Suthari *et al.* 2014).

People use medicinal plants singly in their own preparation for the treatment of various ailments on the basis of indigenous knowledge passed on to them generation after generation. Plants have been one of the

important sources of medicines ever since the dawn of human civilization. In spite of tremendous developments in the field of allopathy, plants still remain as one of the major sources of drugs in modern as well as traditional system of medicine throughout the world. The medicinal plants have various methods of preparation and application for different types of ailments and they have various preparation forms like crude, decoction, powder, and crushed and homogenized in water. The preparation and application methods vary based on the type of disease treated and the actual site of the ailment.

Figure-2: Field Observation of Medicinal Plants in the Study Area.

Telangana state has a rich floral diversity due to different topographic, geographical conditions. Out of a total number of 2586 species estimated about 1800 species are found to be medicinal plants in Telangana. The Govt. of Telangana, realizing the rich potential and diversity of Medicinal plants, have initiated efforts not only to conserve the gene pool of Medicinal Plants occurring the forests but also take up ex-situ cultivation to conserve and improve the threatened / endangered / endemic species of Medicinal Plants in the wild. In the present study we find above 246 medicinal plants of 72 families and their medicinal usages and various parts of plants in usage of medicines (Fig. 2). Medicinal plants and their

families, along with plant part usage for remedies in Telangana State has been mentioned. in Table -1. In the present study of the 72 families most dominant family species are Fabaceae, Malvaceae, Lamiaceae, Combretaceae, Rubiaceae, Acanthaceae, Asteraceae, Euphorbiaceae, Apocyanaceae, Amaranthaceae, Moraceae and the remaining family species are less dominant compare to the above families, some of the families representing 2 species and out of 72 families 30 families representing single species and the medicinal plant part usage point of view majority of the plants Root, Bark, Fruit and Leaves are using respectively for the various remedies (Fig.3).

Figure-3: Number of Species in each family wise encountered in the study Area.

Table 1: Medicinal Plants and their usage in Telangana State, India.

S. No.	Botanical Names	Local Names	Family	Part(s)used	Medicinal Uses
1.	<i>Abrus precatorius</i> L.	Gurija	Fabaceae	Seed	Insect bite, Abortifacient,
2.	<i>Abutilon indicum</i> (L.) Sweet	Mudra benda	Malvaceae	Root	Aphrodisiac, Infertility
3.	<i>Acacia chundra</i> (Rottler) Willd.	Sandra	Fabaceae	Bark	Appetite stimulant, Ulcer
4.	<i>Acacia nilotica</i> (L.) Willd. ex Del.	Nalla tumma	Fabaceae	Bark	Burns, Wound healing, scalds
5.	<i>Acalypha indica</i> L.	Penta puti	Euphorbiaceae	Whole Plant	Skin disease
6.	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> L.	Uttareni	Amaranthaceae	Root	Scorpion bite

7.	<i>Acorus calamus</i>	calmus	Araceae	Dried rhizomes.	Drypiles, eczema, scabies, acidity
8.	<i>Adenantha pavonina</i> L.	Bandi guriginja	Fabaceae	Leaf	Dysentery, hemorrhage
9.	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L.) Corrêa	Maredu	Rutaceae	Leaf /Fruit	Skin disease, digestive
10.	<i>Aerva lanata</i> (L.) Juss.	Pindi kura	Amaranthaceae	Leaf	Kidney stones, Wounds
11.	<i>Aerva sanguinolenta</i> (L.) Blume	Konda pindi	Amaranthaceae	Whole Plant	Urinary troubles
12.	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>	Meka kalupu	Asteraceae	Leaf	Antioxidant
13.	<i>Ailanthus excelsa</i> Roxb.	Peda manu	Simaroubaceae	Bark	Anthelmintic,Piles
14.	<i>Alangium salviifolium</i> (L.f.) Wangerin.	Ooduga	Cornaceae	Bark	Snake bite, dog bite
15.	<i>Albizia odoratissima</i> (L.f.) Benth.	Chinduga	Fabaceae	Bark	Leucoderma
16.	<i>Allium cepa</i> Linn.	Garlic	Liliaceae	Bulb,whole plant	Antioxident, anti hypertensive, anti thromboic
17.	<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> Linn	Ponnagantikura	Amaranthaceae	Leaf	Eye, cuts & Wounds, Antidote for snake bite
18.	<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i> L.	Mulla thotakura	Amaranthaceae	Leaf	Appetite stimulant
19.	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i> (Burm.f.)Wall. ex Nees	Nelavemu	Acanthaceae	Whole Plant	Dyspepsia
20.	<i>Anisomeles malabarica</i> (L.) R.Br.ex Sims	Dayyam chettu	Lamiaceae	Whole Plant	Fever
21.	<i>Anodendron paniculatum</i> A.DC.	Athukuduteega	Apocynaceae	Bark	Bone fracture
22.	<i>Anogeissus acuminata</i> (Roxb. ex DC.)Wall. ex Guillem. & Perr.	Pasi	Combretaceae	Leaf	Cough
23.	<i>Annona squamosa</i> L.	Seethaphalam	Annonaceae	Seed	Insect bite, lice in hair, tooth-ache
24.	<i>Argemone mexicana</i> L.	Mulu puccha	Papavaraceae	Whole Plant	Skin disease
25.	<i>Aristolochia indica</i> L.	Nalleswari	Aristolochiaceae	Root	Snake bite
26.	<i>Asparagus gonocladus</i> Baker	Guddelugubochu	Asparagaceae	Tuber	Aphrodisiac
27.	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> Willd.	Pilli teegalu	Asparagaceae	Tuber	Aphrodisiac
28.	<i>Atalantia monophylla</i> DC.	Adavi nimma	Rutaceae	Root	Paralysis
29.	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A.Juss.	Vepa	Meliaceae	Bark	Stomach-ache
30.	<i>Bambusa bambos</i> (L.) Voss	Kanka bongu	Poaceae	Seed	Food
31.	<i>Barleria cristata</i> L.	Neeli gorinta	Acanthaceae	Root	Abortifacient
32.	<i>Barleria montana</i> Nees	Nilambaram	Acanthaceae	Root	Skin disease
33.	<i>Barleria prionitis</i> L.	Mulla gorinta	Acanthaceae	Root	Scorpion bite
34.	<i>Barringtonia acutangula</i> (L.) Gaertn.	Nir kanki	Lecythidaceae	Bark	Arthritis, joint pain, gout
35.	<i>Bauhinia malabarica</i> Roxb.	Puli are	Fabaceae	Bark	Dyspepsia
36.	<i>Bauhinia racemosa</i> Lam.	Are	Fabaceae	Bark	Leucoderma
37.	<i>Bauhinia semla</i> Wunderlin	Goddeti are	Fabaceae	Bark	Tonic
38.	<i>Blumea bifoliata</i> (L.) DC.	Kukka pogaku	Asteraceae	Root	Cough
39.	<i>Blumea virens</i> DC.	Adavi pogaku	Asteraceae	Leaf	Skin disease
40.	<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i> L.	Atika mamidi	Nyctaginaceae	Root and Whole Plant	Fever, tonic
41.	<i>Bombax ceiba</i> L.	Buruga	Bombacaceae	Bark	Cough
42.	<i>Boswellia serrata</i> Roxb. ex Colebr.	Anduga	Burseraceae	Bark	Fever, tonic
43.	<i>Breynia retusa</i> (Dennst.) Alston	Purugudu	Phyllanthaceae	Root	Aphrodisiac
44.	<i>Bridelia montana</i> (Roxb.) Willd.	Panchotkam	Phyllanthaceae	Bark	Antimalarial, Anti diarrhea,
45.	<i>Bridelia retusa</i> (L.) A.Juss.	Korra maddi	Phyllanthaceae	Bark	Anti diarrheal
46.	<i>Buchanania axillaris</i> (Desr.)	Pedda morli	Anacardiaceae	Bark and	Skin disease, back pain

	Ramamoorthy			Gum	
47.	<i>Buchanania cochinchinensis</i> (Lour.) M.R. Almeida	Morri, Morli	Anacardiaceae	Gum	Back pain, laxative
48.	<i>Butea superba</i> Roxb.	Teega moduga	Fabaceae	Bark	Urinary troubles
49.	<i>Calotropis gigantea</i> (L.) Dryand.	Jilledu	Apocynaceae	Root	Snake bite
50.	<i>Canavalia cathartica</i> Thouars	Adavi tamba	Fabaceae	Seed	Scorpion bite
51.	<i>Capparis sepiaria</i> L.	Uppi	Capparaceae	Bark	Stomachic, tonic, skin disease
52.	<i>Capparis zeylanica</i> L.	Aadonda	Capparaceae	Root, fruit	Dyspepsia, tonic
53.	<i>Careya arborea</i> Roxb.	Budadharmi	Lecythidaceae	Fruit, Bark	Cough, appetite stimulant
54.	<i>Casearia nigrescens</i> Tue.	Kanmeswaram	Salicaceae	Bark	Fish poison
55.	<i>Cassia fistula</i> L.	Rela	Fabaceae	Fruit	Diarrhea, diuretic
56.	<i>Cassine glauca</i> (Rottb.) Kuntze	Bhutankush	Celastraceae	Bark	Dyspepsia
57.	<i>Catunaregam spinosa</i> (Thunb.) Tirveng.	Manga	Rubiaceae	Fruit	Laxative
58.	<i>Celosia argentea</i> L.	Gunugu	Amaranthaceae	Leaf	Cuts
59.	<i>Ceriscoides turgida</i> (Roxb.) Tirveng.	Kukka elka	Rubiaceae	Bark	Cough
60.	<i>Chloroxylon swietenia</i> DC.	Bilugu	Rutaceae	Bark	Skin disease
61.	<i>Cissampelos pareira</i> L.	Bodhi	Menispermaceae	Root	Cardiac stimulant
62.	<i>Cissus vitiginea</i> L.	Adavi draksha	Vitaceae	Fruit	Healing power
63.	<i>Cleistanthus collinus</i> (Roxb.) Benth. ex Hook. f.	Nalla kodisa	Phyllanthaceae	Whole Plant	Homicide, fish stupifying
64.	<i>Cleome viscosa</i> L.	Vaminta	Cleomaceae	Whole Plant	Skin disease
65.	<i>Chlorophytum borivilianum</i> Sant. And Fernand.	Safed musli	Liliaceae	Roots.	Aphrodisiac, piles, anorexia, galactagogue, analgesic
66.	<i>Cocculus hirsutus</i> (L.) W. Theob.	Shibbi teega	Menispermaceae	Root	Fever, urinary diseases, stomach disorders
67.	<i>Coldenia procumbens</i> L.	Chepputattaku	Boraginaceae	Whole Plant	Wounds
68.	<i>Combretum albidum</i> G. Don	Yada teega	Combretaceae	Bark	Diarrhea, dysentery
69.	<i>Combretum latifolium</i> Blume	Yada teega	Combretaceae	Bark	Diuretic, anti inflammation
70.	<i>Combretum roxburghii</i> Spreng.	Yadaku	Combretaceae	Bark	Diabetic, diarrhea, malaria
71.	<i>Cordia dichotoma</i> G. Forst.	Iriki	Boraginaceae	Fruit	Dyspepsia
72.	<i>Cordia macleodii</i> Hook. f. & Thomson	Botuku	Boraginaceae	Bark	Jaundice, mouth sores
73.	<i>Crotalaria albida</i> B. Heyne ex Roth	Adavi janumu	Fabaceae	Root	Scorpion bite
74.	<i>Crotalaria ramosissima</i> Roxb.	Tella janumu	Fabaceae	Leaf	Wounds
75.	<i>Crotalaria verrucosa</i> L.	Tella janumu	Fabaceae	Root	Snake bite
76.	<i>Curculigo orchiioides</i> Gaertn.	Nela thadi	Hypoxidaceae	Tuber	Aphrodisiac
77.	<i>Curcuma pseudomontana</i> J. Graham	Adavi pasupu	Zingiberaceae	Tuber	Antiseptic
78.	<i>Cymbopogon flexuosus</i> (Nees ex Steud.) W. Watson	Adavi nimma gaddi	Poaceae	Root, tuber	Tonic
79.	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Thunga	Cyperaceae	Tuber, Root	Tonic, scorpion bite
80.	<i>Cyrtolipsis dubia</i> (Burm. f.) M.R. Almeida	Budda pala	Apocynaceae	Root	Nervous disorders
81.	<i>Dalbergia lanceolaria</i> subsp. <i>paniculata</i> (Roxb.) Thoth.	Porla pachari	Fabaceae	Bark	Baldness
82.	<i>Dalbergia volubilis</i> Roxb.	Teega pachari	Fabaceae	Bark	Skin disease
83.	<i>Dendrophthoe falcata</i> (L. f.) Ettingsh.	Vadanica	Loranthaceae	Whole Plant	Fever
84.	<i>Derris scandens</i> (Roxb.) Benth.	Chakali teega	Fabaceae	Bark	Pains, anti inflammatory

85.	<i>Desmodium gangeticum</i> (L.) DC.	Konda saru	Fabaceae	Root	Scorpion bite
86.	<i>Desmodium triflorum</i> (L.) DC.	Munta mandu	Fabaceae	Root	Hemorrhage
87.	<i>Desmodium velutinum</i> (Willd.) DC.	Teega velga	Fabaceae	Root	Scorpion bite
88.	<i>Dichrostachys cinerea</i> (L.) Wight & Arn.	Veluthuru	Fabaceae	Bark	Skin disease
89.	<i>Dillenia pentagyna</i> Roxb.	Kalinga	Dilleniaceae	Bark, Fruit	Tonic, fever, anti cancer
90.	<i>Dioscorea bulbifera</i> L.	Chenna gadda	Dioscoreaceae	Tuber	Arthritis, fever
91.	<i>Dioscorea pentaphylla</i> L.	Karra pendalam	Dioscoriaceae	tuber	Swelling, burns
92.	<i>Diospyros chloroxylon</i> Roxb.	Illinda	Ebenaceae	Bark, leaf	Burns, rheumatic pain
93.	<i>Diospyros malabarica</i> (Desr.) Kostel.	Konda tuniki	Ebenaceae	Bark	Bronchitis
94.	<i>Diospyros melanoxyton</i> Roxb.	Tuniki	Ebenaceae	Fruit	Dyspepsia, laxative
95.	<i>Diospyros montana</i> Roxb.	Muchi tuniki	Ebenaceae	Bark, Fruit	Anti tumor anthelmintic
96.	<i>Diplocyclos palmatus</i> (L.) C. Jeffrey	Linga donda	Cucurbitaceae	Fruit	Diarrhea
97.	<i>Ehretia laevis</i> Roxb.	Pala danthi	Boraginaceae	Fruit	Dyspepsia
98.	<i>Eriolaena hookeriana</i> Wight & Arn.	Bothuku	Malvaceae	Bark	Stomach ache
99.	<i>Erythrina suberosa</i> Roxb.	Muli moduga	Fabaceae	Bark	Veterinary, appetite stimulant
100.	<i>Erythroxylum monogynum</i> Roxb.	Deva daru	Erythroxylaceae	Fruit	Tonic
101.	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> L.	Reddivari nanubalu	Euphorbiaceae	Leaf	Wounds
102.	<i>Euphorbia nivulia</i> Buch.-Ham.	Aku jemudu	Euphorbiaceae	Latex	Bone fracture
103.	<i>Ficus benghalensis</i> L.	Marri	Moraceae	Latex	Wounds
104.	<i>Ficus hispida</i> L.f.	Bomma medi	Moraceae	Leaf	Bone fracture
105.	<i>Ficus microcarpa</i> L.f.	Juvvi	Moraceae	Bark	Leucoderma
106.	<i>Ficus racemosa</i> L.	Medi	Moraceae	Leaf	Bone fracture
107.	<i>Ficus tinctoria</i> subsp. <i>gibbosa</i> (Blume) Corner	Adavi barrenka	Moraceae	Bark	Diarrhea, constipation
108.	<i>Ficus virens</i> Aiton	Banda juvvi	Moraceae	Bark	Rheumatism
109.	<i>Flacourtia indica</i> (Burm.f.) Merr.	Kanregu	Salicaceae	Leaf	Scorpion bite
110.	<i>Flemingia macrophylla</i> (Willd.) Merr.	Err puvvu	Fabaceae	Root	Skin disease
111.	<i>Flemingia strobilifera</i> (L.) W.T. Aiton	Adavi chappa	Fabaceae	Root	Skin disease
112.	<i>Gardenia latifolia</i> Aiton	Pedda karinga	Rubiaceae	Bark	Rheumatism, veterinary
113.	<i>Gardenia resinifera</i> Roth	Karinga	Rubiaceae	Bark	Neck pains
114.	<i>Garuga pinnata</i> Roxb.	Garugu	Burseraceae	Bark, fruit	Cancer, stomach ache, Asthma
115.	<i>Getonia floribunda</i> Roxb.	Bontha	Combretaceae	Bark, leaves	Laxative, leprosy anthelmintic
116.	<i>Gisekia pharnaceoides</i> L.	Iska rasi	Gisekiaceae	Whole plant	Pains
117.	<i>Glochidion zeylanicum</i> (Gaertn.) A. Juss.	Neeralli	Phyllanthaceae	Bark	Anti aging, antioxidant
118.	<i>Gloriosa superba</i> L.	Kanda Nabi	Colchicaceae	Root	Arthritis, piles, leprosy, skin
119.	<i>Gmelina arborea</i> Roxb.	Gummadi tekku	Lamiaceae	Bark	Anti-inflammatory, veterinary
120.	<i>Grewia damine</i> Gaertn.	Adavi jana	Malvaceae	Fruit	Laxative
121.	<i>Grewia hirsuta</i> Vahl	Jibilika	Malvaceae	Fruit	Laxative
122.	<i>Grewia rothii</i> DC.	Jana, Chinnajana	Malvaceae	Fruit	Laxative
123.	<i>Grewia tiliifolia</i> Vahl	Tada	Malvaceae	Bark, leaf	Wounds, urinary infection, skin

124.	<i>Gymnosporia emarginata</i> (Willd.) Thwaites	Danthi	Celastraceae	Bark	Skin disease
125.	<i>Haldina cordifolia</i> (Roxb.) Ridsdale	Bandaru	Rubiaceae	Bark	Wounds, Jaundice
126.	<i>Hardwickia binata</i> Roxb.	Narepa	Fabaceae	Bark	Water purifier, gonorrhoea
127.	<i>Helicteres isora</i> L.	Nulthada	Malvaceae	Bark	Veterinary
128.	<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i> (L.) R.Br. ex Schult.	Sugandhi pala	Apocynaceae	Root	Blood purifier, sugar control
129.	<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i> var. <i>pubescens</i> (Wight & Arn.) Hook.f.	Barre sugandhi pala	Apocynaceae	Root	Diabetes
130.	<i>Hemigraphis latebrosa</i> (Roth) Nees	Akkala	Acanthaceae	Rootoot	Anti-alcoholic agent
131.	<i>Hibiscus panduriformis</i> Burm.f.	Adavi benda	Malvaceae	Root	Skin disease
132.	<i>Holarrhena pubescens</i> Wall ex G.Don	Istari pala	Apocynaceae	Bark	Dysentery
133.	<i>Holoptelea integrifolia</i> Planch.	Nemali nara	Ulmaceae	Leaf	Skin disease
134.	<i>Hybanthus enneaspermus</i> (L.) F.Muell.	Nela kobbari	Violaceae	Whole Plant	Aphrodisiac, gonorrhea, urinary infection
135.	<i>Hygrophila auriculata</i> (Schumach.) Heine	Gorimidi	Acanthaceae	Leaf	Dropsy
136.	<i>Hyptis suaveolens</i> (L.) Poit.	Mabeera	Lamiaceae	Leaf	Antiinsecticide, exzema, headache
137.	<i>Indigofera cassioides</i> Rottler ex DC.	Karu kandi	Fabaceae	Root	Scorpion bite
138.	<i>Ipomoea coptica</i> (L.) Roth ex Roem. & Schult.	Suvarchala	Convolvulaceae	Leaf	Mouth wash
139.	<i>Ipomoea eriocarpa</i> R.Br.	Elika chevi	Convolvulaceae	Root	Stomach-ache
140.	<i>Ipomoea hederifolia</i> L.	Kashiratnam	Convolvulaceae	Root	Tonic
141.	<i>Ipomoea obscura</i> (L.) Ker Gawl.	Macha aku	Convolvulaceae	Leaf	Insect bite
142.	<i>Ixora arborea</i> Roxb. ex Sm.	Korivi	Rubiaceae	Bark	Appetite stimulant
143.	<i>Justicia betonica</i> L.	Pedda nilambaram	Acanthaceae	Root	Mental disorders
144.	<i>Kavalama urens</i> (Roxb.) Raf.	Tabasi	Malvaceae	Bark	Appetite stimulant
145.	<i>Kydia calycina</i> Roxb.	Konda patti	Malvaceae	Bark	Dyspepsia
146.	<i>Lagerstroemia parviflora</i> Roxb.	Chennangi	Lythraceae	Bark	Anti-darrheal, anti-obesity
147.	<i>Lannea coromandelica</i> (Houtt.) Merr.	Dumpena, Dumpidi	Anacardiaceae	Bark	Antiseptic, appetite stimulant
148.	<i>Leea asiatica</i> (L.) Ridsdale	Velama sandi	Vitaceae	Root	Skin disease
149.	<i>Lepidagathis cristata</i> Willd.	Nakka peetirigadda	Acanthaceae	Whole Plant	Fever, fits
150.	<i>Leucas aspera</i> (Willd.) Link	Thummi	Lamiaceae	Leaf	Healing power
151.	<i>Leucas decemdentata</i> (Willd.) Sm.	Konda tummi	Lamiaceae	Leaf	Skin disease
152.	<i>Limonia acidissima</i> L.	Velaga	Rutaceae	Fruit	Tonic
153.	<i>Lindernia ciliata</i> (Colsm.) Pennell	Nela rampi	Linderniaceae	Whole Plant	Skin disease
154.	<i>Litsea glutinosa</i> (Lour.) C.B. Rob.	Narra mamidi	Lauraceae	Bark	All diseases
155.	<i>Madhuca longifolia</i> var. <i>latifolia</i> (Roxb.) A.Chev.	Ippa	Sapotaceae	Flower, Seed	Dyspepsia, hair oil
156.	<i>Mallotus philippensis</i> (Lam.) Müll.Arg.	Kunkuma	Euphorbiaceae	Seed	Leucoderma
157.	<i>Mangifera indica</i> L.	Konda mamidi	Anacardiaceae	Bark, Fuit	Appetite stimulant, tonic
158.	<i>Manilkara hexandra</i> (Roxb.) Dubard	Pala	Sapotaceae	Fruit	Laxative

159.	<i>Memecylon umbellatum</i> Burm.f.	Alli	Melastomataceae	Root	Diuretic
160.	<i>Merremia hederacea</i> (Burm.f.)Hallier f.	Talantu teega	Convolvulaceae	Fruit	Hair wash
161.	<i>Microstachys chamaelea</i> (L.) Müll.Arg.	Isaka	Euphorbiaceae	Root	Skin disease
162.	<i>Milusa tomentosa</i> (Roxb.) J.Sinclair	Barre duddi	Annonaceae	Bark	Body swelling, weakness
163.	<i>Millingtonia hortensis</i> L.f.	Boda malle	Bignoniaceae	Bark	Bronchitis
164.	<i>Mimosa hamata</i> Willd.	Magadadi	Fabaceae	Bark	Aphrodisiac
165.	<i>Mitragyna parvifolia</i> (Roxb.) Korth.	Batta ganapa	Rubiaceae	Bark	Muscular pain, aphrodisiac
166.	<i>Momordica charantia</i> L.	Kakara	Cucurbitaceae	Fruit	Diabetes
167.	<i>Momordica dioica</i> Roxb. ex Willd.	Boda kakara	Cucurbitaceae	Fruit	Diabetes
168.	<i>Morinda pubescens</i> Sm.	Togara mogili	Rubiaceae	Bark	Appetite stimulant, anthrax
169.	<i>Moringa pterygosperma</i> Gaertn.	Munaga	Moringaceae	Bark	Aphrodisiac
170.	<i>Mucuna pruriens</i> (L.) DC.	Dula gondi	Fabaceae	Seed	Abortifacient, aphrodisiac
171.	<i>Mullago pentaphylla</i> L.	Chitharasi	Mulluginaceae	Whole Plant	Diuretic, appetizer
172.	<i>Nyctanthes arbor-tristis</i> L.	Karise	Oleaceae	Bark	Bone fracture
173.	<i>Ochna obtusata</i> DC.	Sonnari	Ochnaceae	Bark	Asthma, constipation
174.	<i>Ocimum americanum</i> L.	Kukka tulasi	Lamiaceae	Leaf	Antiseptic
175.	<i>Oroxylum indicum</i> (L.) Kurz	Dundilam	Bignoniaceae	Bark	Rheumatism
176.	<i>Osbeckia stellata</i> Buch.-Ham. ex Ker Gawl.	Adavi gulabi	Melastomataceae	Root	Abortifacient
177.	<i>Paederia foetida</i> L.	Savirela	Rubiaceae	Leaf	Skin disease
178.	<i>Paracalyx scariosus</i> (Roxb.) Ali	Adavi tellakandi	Fabaceae	Root	Skin disease
179.	<i>Pentanema indicum</i> (L.) Ling	Adavi chamanti	Asteraceae	Root	Abortifacient
180.	<i>Pergularia daemia</i> (Forssk.) Chiov.	Dustapu teega	Apocynaceae	Whole Plant	Respiratory disease
181.	<i>Peristrophe paniculata</i> (Forssk.)Brummitt	Chebura	Acanthaceae	Leaf	Skin disease
182.	<i>Phoenix loureiroi</i> Kunth	Jittetha	Arecaceae	Fruit	Laxative
183.	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i> Schumach.& Thonn.	Nela usiri	Phyllanthaceae	Whole Plant	Jaundice
184.	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> L.	Usiri	Phyllanthaceae	Whole Plant	Tonic
185.	<i>Phyllanthus urinaria</i> L.	Yerra usiri	Phyllanthaceae	Whole Plant	Jaundice
186.	<i>Phyllodium pulchellum</i> (L.) Desv.	Sarivi	Fabaceae	Roothole Plant	Scorpion bite
187.	<i>Physalis minima</i> L.	Buddabudasa	Solanaceae	Whole plant	Diuretic, laxative, antipyretic
188.	<i>Pistia stratiotes</i> L.	Antara thamara	Araceae	Whole Plant	Baldness
189.	<i>Plectranthus mollis</i> (Aiton) Spreng.	Nela marri	Lamiaceae	Root	Scorpion bite
190.	<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i> L.	Chitramulam	Plumbaginaceae	Root	Boils
191.	<i>Polyalthia cerasoides</i> (Roxb.) Bedd.	Chiluka duddi	Annonaceae	Bark	Seed tonic
192.	<i>Polycarpaea corymbosa</i> (L.) Lam.	Gaddi puvvu	Caryophyllaceae	Rot	Snake bite
193.	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i> (L.) Pierre	Kanuga	Fabaceae	Bark	Skin disease
194.	<i>Pterospermum xylocarpum</i> (Gaertn.)Santapau & Wagh	Lolugu	Malvaceae	Bark	Joint pain, gout
195.	<i>Pueraria tuberosa</i> (Willd.) DC.	Nela gummadi	Fabaceae	Tuber	All diseases
196.	<i>Pupalia lappacea</i> (L.) Juss.	Gundu uttareneni	Amaranthaceae	Leaf	Insect bite
197.	<i>Putranjiva roxburghii</i> Wall.	Putranjiva	Putranjivaceae	Bark	Bronchitis

198.	<i>Recinus communis</i> L.	Amudam	Euphorbiaceae	Fruit, leaf, seed	Constipation, stomach ache, insomnia
199.	<i>Rhynchosia suaveolens</i> (L.f.) DC.	Adavi kandi	Fabaceae	Seed	Dysentery
200.	<i>Rivea hypocrateriformis</i> Choisy	Boddi kura	Convolvulaceae	Root	Snake bite
201.	<i>Sapindus emarginatus</i> Vahl	Kunkudu	Sapindaceae	Fruit	Hair wash
202.	<i>Schleichera oleosa</i> (Lour.) Merr.	Pusuku	Sapindaceae	Bark	Dyspepsia
203.	<i>Schrebera swietenoides</i> Roxb.	Mokkam	Oleaceae	Bark	Urinary problems, Stomachache
204.	<i>Scleria levis</i> Retz.	Ashta medha	Cyperaceae	Root	Blood purifier
205.	<i>Scoparia dulcis</i> L.	Oosari	Plantaginaceae	Whole Plant	Menstrual pains
206.	<i>Semecarpus anacardium</i> L.f.	Nalla jeedi	Anacardiaceae	Seed	Wounds
207.	<i>Senna alata</i> (L.) Roxb.		Fabaceae	Leaf	Skin disease
208.	<i>Senna occidentalis</i> (L.) Link	Adavi chennangi	Fabaceae	Fruit	Appetite stimulant
209.	<i>Senna tora</i> (L.) Roxb.	Tagarisa	Fabaceae	Leaf	Insect bite
210.	<i>Sida acuta</i> Burm.f.	Chilka parre	Malvaceae	Root	Mental disorders
211.	<i>Sida cordata</i> (Burm.f.) Borss. Waalk.	Gaya paku	Malvaceae	Root	Tonic
212.	<i>Sida cordifolia</i> L.	Chiru benda	Malvaceae	Root	Appetite stimulant
213.	<i>Smilax perfoliata</i> Lour.	Nageti dumpa	Smilacaceae	Tuber	Abortifacient
214.	<i>Solanum virginianum</i> L.	Vakudu	Solanaceae	Fruit	Laxative
215.	<i>Sophora velutina</i> Lindl.	Adavi kanuga	Fabaceae	Bark	Appetite stimulant
216.	<i>Soymida febrifuga</i> (Roxb.) A.Juss.	Somi	Meliaceae	Bark	Tonic, diuretic
217.	<i>Sphaeranthus indicus</i> L.	Bodasaram	Asteraceae	Whole Plant	Kill lice in domestic fowl
218.	<i>Stereospermum chelonoides</i> (L.f.) DC.	Kalagoru	Bignoniaceae	Bark	Astringent, wound healing
219.	<i>Streblus asper</i> Lour.	Barrenka	Moraceae	Tender Shoot	Tooth brush
220.	<i>Strychnos nux-vomica</i> L.	Visha mushti	Loganiaceae	Bark	Snake bite, antiseptic
221.	<i>Strychnos potatorum</i> L.f.	Chilla	Loganiaceae	Seed	Eye disease
222.	<i>Symphorema involucreatum</i> Roxb.	Konda takkali	Lamiaceae	Bark	Snake bile, scorpion bite
223.	<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.) Skeels	Neredu	Myrtaceae	Bark, Fruit	Tonic, diabetes
224.	<i>Tamarindus indica</i> L.	Chinta	Fabaceae	Bark	Scorpion bite
225.	<i>Tamilnadia uliginosa</i> (Retz.) Tirveng. & Sastre	Guvvenka	Rubiaceae	Bark	Stomach ache, burns
226.	<i>Tectona grandis</i> L.f.	Teku	Lamiaceae	Bark	Abortifacient
227.	<i>Tephrosia purpurea</i> (L.) Pers.	Vempali	Fabaceae	Root	Easy delivery
228.	<i>Terminalia arjuna</i> (Roxb. ex DC.) Wight & Arn.	Yeru maddi, Tella maddi	Combretaceae	Bark	Wounds, heart disease
229.	<i>Terminalia bellirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb.	Tani	Combretaceae	Fruit	Hepatitis, asthma, piles
230.	<i>Terminalia chebula</i> Retz.	Karakkaya	Combretaceae	Fruit	Constipation, Cough, colic pain
231.	<i>Thespesia lampas</i> (Cav.) Dalzell & A.Gibson	Adavi patti	Malvaceae	Root	Fever, diuretic
232.	<i>Tragia involucrata</i> L.	Dula gondi	Euphorbiaceae	Root	Scorpion bite
233.	<i>Trichodesma indicum</i> (L.) Lehm.	Gabba	Boraginaceae	Leaf	Diuretic, ophthalmic
234.	<i>Tridax procumbens</i> (L.) L.	Nalla alam	Asteraceae	Leaf	Hemorrhage, cuts
235.	<i>Triumfetta rhomboidea</i> Jacq.	Marla benda	Malvaceae	Root	Galactagogue
236.	<i>Urena lobata</i> L.	Pedda benda	Malvaceae	Rootoot	Skin disease
237.	<i>Vanda tessellata</i> (Roxb.) Hook. ex G. Don	Kodikallachettu	Orchidaceae	Root	Bronchitis, piles
238.	<i>Ventilago maderaspatana</i> Gaertn.	Galivana teega	Rhamnaceae	Bark	Anthrax, leprosy

239.	<i>Vernonia cinerea</i> (L.) Less.	Garita kamma	Asteraceae	leaf	Respiratory infections
240.	<i>Vernonia cinerea</i> var. <i>parviflora</i> (Reinw. ex Blume) DC.	Adavi garita kamma	Asteraceae	Root	Digestive, skin diseases
241.	<i>Waltheria indica</i> L.	Nalla benda	Malvaceae	Leaf	Insect bite, malaria
242.	<i>Woodfordia fruticosa</i> (L.) Kurz	Jaji	Lythraceae	Bark	Tonic, stomach ache
243.	<i>Xylia xylocarpa</i> (Roxb.) Taub.	Bojja	Fabaceae	Bark	Skin disease
244.	<i>Ziziphus oenopolia</i> (L.) Mill.	Pariki	Rhamnaceae	Fruit	Diuretic, imanagogue
245.	<i>Ziziphus rugosa</i> Lam.	Enugu pariki	Rhamnaceae	Leaf	Bone fracture, teeth ache
246.	<i>Ziziphus xylopyrus</i> (Retz.) Willd.	Gotte	Rhamnaceae	Leaf	Skin disease, Dandruff

It is evident that the Indian people have tremendous passion for medicinal plants and use of them for wide range of health related applications from a common cold to memory improvement and treatment of poisonous snake bites to a cure for muscular dystrophy and the enhancement of body's general immunity. In the oral traditions local communities in every ecosystem based on that we have discovered the medicinal uses of plants found locally in their ecosystem. It is evident that the utility of plants varied. Diversity exists not only in plants but also in their utilization for different ailments. In some cases the whole plant has been found useful while in others the plant parts (root, leaves, stem, bark, oil, flowers, fruits, corm and seed) seems to have been used as curative agents.

CONCLUSION

Plants have been used as medicine, foods, agrochemicals and pharmaceuticals by large number of People around the globe. Especially India is one the mega biodiversity country with 15 types of agro climatic zones with the potential source of biodiversity in that our Telangana state has a rich floral diversity with different topographic conditions and our people have a indigenous and good specific knowledge on plants and plant based resources utilization for the most of remedies their survival even in most of the pandemics. Most of them are dependent on Forests and natural resources and biodiversity. Therefore documenting the medicinal plants and associated indigenous knowledge can be used as a basis for developing management plans for conservation and sustainable use of medicinal plants for the processing of medicines, biochemical synthesis, pharmacopeia and pharmacological studies and application of it for the future sustenance.

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